

Name

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Gasoline Engine Don't Have a Future in Our Transportation

Interpretation (26)

As the society is becoming more concerned for the environment and people are going for nature-friendly options for transportation, the days of gasoline engine are numbered.

Analysis (406)

The transportation industry takes many natural resources from the earth causing various negative effects in the environment including global warming (Pischinger, 2004; p. 5). Today around 97 percent of our vehicles are consuming petroleum-based energy. In 1990, the carbon dioxide emission grew vigorously in the transportation sector. It is estimated that the emission would rise about 40 percent in 2025 and half of this increase would be contributed by the transportation industry. The shortage of the natural resources due to excessive use of its products and the future emission laws development, force to bring a more environment-friendly and efficient thrust system for engines.

Hybrid propulsion systems and fuel cell systems are the new alternatives to existing diesel and gasoline engines (Brown & Morishima, 2002: p. 2 8). In all possible alternatives, natural gas is also an attractive fuel for the future of transportation along with other fuel modes. The positive aspects of this fuel type are that it is low cost, decreases CO₂-emission. Number of wholly natural gas modes of transportation is increasing as the numbers of gas stations are rising around the globe. In this type of engines gas is stored on high pressure as around 200 bar and is induced into the specific ports through injectors alike to those installed in gasoline engines (Yasar et al, 2013; p.1277). Although natural gas is not environmental friendly and can cause a lack of another important natural resource if used excessively, but in terms of cost it is quite a good option specially for mass transportation.

There are two major drawbacks of gasoline engines; the first one is that it is expensive. As the countries and communities have come closer, the usage of different transportations for trade, supplies and travelling has touched sky height (Pischinger, 2004; p. 8). The high rates of petroleum products raise inflation, unemployment, recession and other economic and social issues within the societies. The second disadvantage of gasoline is the emission of harmful gases within the environment. The electric cars provide opportunity to flourish the transportation industry without loss of the natural resources and polluting the environment. Nissan Leaf and Chevy Volt have come up with all electric automobiles, which show the increasing penetration of second-generation bio-fuels (Jianyong et al, 2014; p. 295). The raising prices of gasoline have made natural gas more attractive to be consumed as fuel. Through Hydraulic, drilling and hydraulic fracturing natural gases have also become more accessible domestically.

Evaluation (27)

Pischinger argument is biased on the concept that homegrown natural gases and electric cars would replace gasoline and diesel engines in the near future of transportation.

Inference (28)

Today people want low carbon, cheap fuel and need energy security for the future. Therefore search for efficient substitutes of gasoline and diesel engines is a global issue.

Explanation (22)

As the demand of transportation is raising the needs of fuel-efficient vehicles and environment, friendly energy for transportation modes is crucial.

Self-Regulation (31)

My approach is that electric car engines can definitely be a nature friendly and cheap alternative of gasoline but these cars should be less expensive and easily available in local markets.

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